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A Creative Folio

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The Flip Side

I wished in the serenity of the moon,
With lunar light beaming through my room,
A desperate plea for a turn of events,
To live the flip side of life, free of torment.

I plead to be the loved, not the lover,
To be cherished, not the keeper,
The one seen, not the one looking,
The one chosen, without begging.

Simply make me the scenery,
Or the flowers, let me be
Just not the painter,
Just not the gardener.

The poetry, not the poet,
The melody in a duet,
The one who simply sits still,
Not the one turning the wheel.

I'm lost.
I'm tired.
I want to be found,
Not the one left behind.

Oh, how sublime it is to be held,
Not the one holding, not the one leading;
To be served, provided, adored,
Not the servant bound to endless toil.

'Will you hear my list if I keep going?
For my misery seems unending'
Let my tears reach the heaven's door
My faith won't keep me sane anymore.

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I longed to be privileged, or barely a damsel,
Not the weary heroine forcing everything to happen!
For once, let me receive there is for my hands
A penny, time, pity... or even just peace of mind.

'Dear child,' a warm voice I heard.
'Am I not answering your prayer from before?
You asked for love, so I removed and brought in people
For you to love yourself and those unlovable.

Didn't you once ask for wealth?
Hence, I gave first a little you can cherish
That in bits of things, you know their true value
And I will grant abundance once you learn this too.

Didn't you ask for joy the most?
But joy won't come from the things you labor
My plans will give you more reasons to smile
Keep moving and you'll be happier after a while.

But there is more than what you cried
More precious than all the treasures combined
For in your struggles, when you've been fighting along
You are being taught, refined and built strong.

I have for you the best that could be given
Tell me, have you not liked your life changing?
My child, this life of yours is not random
Hear me, this is all you have wished for
Wisdom.